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Impact Factor: 0.98

SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT: THEORY, PRACTICE AND FUTURE CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The purpose of this paper is to critically assess current developments in the theory and practice of supply chain management and through such an assessment to identify barriers, possibilities and key trends. This paper summarises the key elements in supply chain management theory. It presents a number of challenges to existing thinking about supply strategy and supply chain management

Keywords: Supply chain management, Suppliers, Strategic management, Sustainability

Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

Supply Chain Management (SCM) encompasses every effort involved in producing and delivering a final product or service, from the supplier to the customer.

Supply Chain Management includes managing supply and demand, sourcing raw materials and parts, manufacturing and assembly, warehousing and inventory tracking, order entry and order management, distribution across all channels, and delivery to the customer.

SCM is an integrating function with primary responsibility for linking major business functions and business processes within and across companies into a cohesive and high-performing business model. It includes all of the logistics management activities noted above, as well as manufacturing operations, and it drives coordination of processes and activities with and across marketing, sales, product design, finance, and information technology

SCM is the management of the flow of goods and services. It includes the movement and storage of raw materials, work-in-process inventory, and finished goods from point of origin to point of consumption.

challenges

The supply chain makes the world go round. It connects everything to each other.

Ever wonder about the process used to make your computer or phone screen you're reading this from? Nope, me neither. But without some sort of supply chain management, such technological feats would be impossible, as would pretty much every material thing you possess.

Supply chain practice is interrogated through a series of four fundamental questions:

- (1) Who was “managing the supply chain” in practice? (That is, which individuals or groups are actually engaged in such practice?)
- (2) What type of “supply chain” activities were they managing?
- (3) What were the key enablers and inhibitors to this process?
- (4) What external factors were driving the strategic imperative of supply chain management?

FIGURE: Scope of the six supply chains studied

There are two distinct supply chain management strategies: (1) risk and (2) opportunities, which are influenced by different intentions (assess and reduce risks versus increase and realize opportunities). They have an emphasis on different issues (eliminate existing and

potential problems at production sites and suppliers versus realize sustainability-driven product designs) and aim to achieve different results (e.g., reduce negative effects versus create positive effects).

Management of sustainability risks and opportunities often follows a different logic with regard to design, production, products and supply chains, and thus leads to different foci for the sustainability performance of supply chains. Sustainable supply chain management is posited to stem from a business model where economic goals are compatible with environmental and social goals. Managers continue to struggle with adopting and implementing sustainability internally and across their supply chain. More effective decision making regarding when and how to adopt and implement Sustainable supply chain management is posited to stem from a business model where economic goals are compatible with environmental and social goals. Managers continue to struggle with adopting and implementing sustainability internally and across their supply chain. More effective decision making regarding when and how to adopt and implement sustainability and supply chain management (SSCM) can help managers throughout the supply chain to understand the complexities they face as they encounter both the operational and social challenges of sustainability.

Empirical evidence shows that investments in sustainable supply chain management can improve economic-based performance. Thus, based on standard economic theory, rational business decision makers should and will implement sustainable supply chain management practices.

By offering insight into how managers in organizations experience and make decisions about SSCM, this grounded research helps advance theory and knowledge in the arena of business sustainability and supply chain management (SSCM) can help managers throughout the supply chain to understand the complexities they face as they encounter both the operational and social challenges of sustainability.

By offering insight into how managers in non-exemplar SSCM organizations experience and make decisions about SSCM, this grounded research helps advance theory and knowledge in the arena of business sustainability and supply chain management.

The supply chain—a term now commonly used internationally—encompasses every effort involved in producing and delivering a final product or service, from the supplier's to the customer's. To be involved in this process is a career in ensuring the whole world works.

Managers increasingly find themselves assigned the role of the rope in a very real tug of war pulled one way by customers' mounting demands and the opposite way by the company's need for growth and profitability. Many have discovered that they can keep the rope from snapping and, in fact, achieve profitable growth by treating supply chain management as a strategic variable.

These savvy managers recognize two important things. First, they think about the supply chain as a whole—all the links involved in managing the flow of products, services, and information from their suppliers' suppliers to their customers' customers (that is, channel customers, such as distributors and retailers). Second, they pursue tangible outcomes—focused on revenue growth, asset utilization, and cost.

Rejecting the traditional view of a company and its component parts as distinct functional entities, these managers realize that the real measure of success is how well activities coordinate across the supply chain to create value for customers, while increasing the profitability of every link in the chain.

This analysis of initiatives to improve supply chain management by more than 100 manufacturers, distributors, and retailers shows many making great progress, while others fail dismally. The successful initiatives that have contributed to profitable growth share several themes. They are typically broad efforts, combining both strategic and tactical change. They

also reflect a holistic approach, viewing the supply chain from end to end and orchestrating efforts so that the whole improvement achieved-in revenue, costs, and asset utilization-is greater than the sum of its parts.

- Principle 1: Segment customers based on the service needs of distinct groups and adapt the supply chain to serve these segments profitably.
- Principle 2: Customize the logistics network to the service requirements and profitability of customer segments.
- Principle 3: Listen to market signals and align demand planning accordingly across the supply chain, ensuring consistent forecasts and optimal resource allocation.
- Principle 4: Differentiate product closer to the customer and speed conversion across the supply chain.
- Principle 5: Manage sources of supply strategically to reduce the total cost of owning materials and services.
- Principle 6: Develop a supply chain-wide technology strategy that supports multiple levels of decision making and gives a clear view of the flow of products, services, and information.
- Principle 7: Adopt channel-spanning performance measures to gauge collective success in reaching the end-user effectively and efficiently.

Processes of Supply Chain

- Planning: Plan all Activities involved in sourcing, conversion and logistics management
- Collaboration: Working with Suppliers, intermediaries, third-party service providers and customers
- Execution: Managing and coordinating the movement of materials, information and funds
- Performance Management: Analysis of performance and efficiency of operation

Supply chain management/Operational Analysis

How Supply Chain Operates:

Supply chain management is an example of ISM and has benefited people in many ways such as providing solutions to connect information from all different organizations. It maximizes the use of human power thus reducing the time and costs of training the workers, which could be further deployed to do other more important tasks which increases productivity and efficiency of the company.

Supplier-----> manufacturer-----> wholesaler-----> retailer-----> consumer

4 Big Decision areas in Supply Chain Management

1. Location Decisions:

The geographic placement of production facilities, storage facilities, and resource sourcing is the first step in creating a supply chain. Once the size, number, and location of these factors are determined, the possible paths by which the product flows through to the final customer can be determined too. These decisions are important since they represent the basic strategy for accessing customer markets, and will have a considerable impact on revenue, cost, and

level of service. Other factors to consider: production costs, taxes, duties and duty drawback, tariffs, local content, distribution costs, production limitations, etc.

2. Production Decisions:

The factors to consider include what products to produce, and which plants to produce them in, allocation of suppliers to plants, plants to Data Channel's (DC, and DC's to customer markets. These are important decisions on the revenues, costs and customer service levels of the firm. Another critical issue is the capacity of the manufacturing facilities--and this largely depends the degree of vertical integration within the firm. These decisions include the construction of the master production schedules, scheduling production on machines, and equipment maintenance. Other considerations include workload balancing, and quality control measures at a production facility.

3. Inventory Decisions:

Inventories exist either raw materials, semi-finished or finished goods. They can also be in-process between locations. Since holding of inventories can cost anywhere between 20 to 40 percent of their value, their efficient management is critical in supply chain operations. It is strategic considering that top management sets goals. The determination of the optimal levels of order quantities and reorder points, and setting safety stock levels at each stocking location. These levels are critical, since they are primary determinants of customer service levels.

4. Transportation Decisions:

While air shipments may be fast, reliable, and warrant lesser safety stocks, they are expensive. Meanwhile shipping by sea or rail (land) may be much cheaper, but they necessitate holding relatively large amounts of inventory to buffer against the inherent uncertainty associated with them.

Therefore, customer service levels and geographic location play vital roles in such decisions. Since transportation is more than 30 percent of the logistics costs, operating efficiently makes good economic sense. Shipment sizes (consolidated bulk shipments versus Lot-for-Lot), routing and scheduling of equipment are key in effective management of the firm's transport strategy

The debate in the academic world still continued regarding answers to such questions as: What is supply chain management?

What should it be? Is supply chain management a fad, or here to stay?

Supply chain management as philosophy has both theoretical and managerial implications, and is related to the firm's orientation, viewing the way that the firm integrates supply chain implications throughout the decisions that the organization makes. It asks the question, whether and how does the organization consider supply chain impacts when it makes decisions?

Finally, supply chain management as a function is primarily managerially oriented and considers whether SCM is a functional area in its own right.

Gibson et al. (2005) find that the most common definition practitioners have of supply chain management is as a combination of strategy and activity, whereas Burgess et al. (2006) categorize processes and activities separately, with activities as a single element of a process. In this analysis, processes and activities are both placed under the process category.

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Drivers

Supply chain management is becoming of increasing strategic importance, and the fieldwork concurred with the literature in identifying globalisation, outsourcing and fragmentation as three major drivers.

However, an additional driver was also uncovered that did not feature so predominantly in the literature – market polarisation. It could be argued that this potentially has the most significant effect of all. For Pharma companies, Household products companies and Television companies the mid-high markets that they traditionally served have disappeared and been replaced by a polarised high-end/low-end market profile.

Electronics companies have such a broad range of products that these naturally fall into polar extremes of the volume: variety continuum yet the supply chain strategy used to deliver these products are not significantly different. This has serious implications for supply chain management.

With greater customer sophistication, increasing network fragmentation, and fast-paced globalisation, the primary role of supply chain management, along with the coordination of material, information and cash flows, has become complex. SCM is a multidisciplinary programme designed to help you conceive innovative strategies and deploy differentiated solutions that can help your organisation serve customers in an optimal fashion.

Key Benefits

- Adopt value as a guiding principle to deliver superior managerial performance with significant business impact
- Discover tools to align core processes resulting in the achievement of operational excellence
- Understand frameworks to manage risks and opportunities for sustainable supply chain management on a global scale

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SCM is the oversight of materials, information, and finances as they move in a process from supplier to manufacturer to wholesaler to retailer to consumer. Supply chain management involves coordinating and integrating these flows both within and among companies. It is said that the ultimate goal of any effective supply chain management system is to reduce inventory (with the assumption that products are available when needed). As a solution for successful supply chain management, sophisticated software systems with Web interfaces are competing with Web-based application service providers (ASP) who promise to provide part or all of the SCM service for companies who rent their service.

Supply chain management flows can be divided into three main flows:

- The product flow
- The information flow
- The finances flow

The product flow includes the movement of goods from a supplier to a customer, as well as any customer returns or service needs. The information flow involves transmitting orders and updating the status of delivery. The financial flow consists of credit terms, payment schedules, and consignment and title ownership arrangements

Supply Chain Management (SCM) is an integral process in a variety of industrial sectors. The growth of Information technology (IT) has led to the development of various software programs that can support the SCM process. One such product is supply chain management software.

Key Functions of Supply chain management software

Supply chain management software (SCMS) is designed to perform the following functions:

1. Processing Customer Requirements: SCMS can help enhance the speed of customer requirement processing. This includes checking for raw material availability, product manufacturing, and passing the product to the logistics team. The software can track the entire process, and ensure that the product is delivered on time.
2. Inventory Management: In warehouses, managers can use SCMS to effectively manage the quantity of stocked goods. The software can also help support inventory concerns such as asset management, replenishment lead time, and future inventory and price forecasting.

3. Purchase Order Processing: With SCMS, the purchase order processes are usually automated. It reduces time and effort needed to generate and manage purchase orders. Pre-defined parameters can be set up to replenish inventories, generate serial numbers for product shipments, and track inventory costs.

4. Supplier Relationship Management: The strategic planning and managing of all supplier interactions can be accomplished with SCMS. The software can be used to assess the suppliers' assets and capabilities and compare them with the organizations business strategy.

5. Warehouse Management: SCMS can effectively support a warehouse management system in the movement and storage of products. SCMS can quickly process transactions such a picking, placing, receiving, and shipping.

Using talent supply chain management to overcome challenges in the professional services market

Most organizations are familiar with the discipline of supply chain management (SCM); the process of planning, implementing and controlling the operations of supply chain to satisfy customer requirements as efficiently as possible. The specifics of SCM – managing the movement, use, and storage of all raw materials, work in progress, and finished goods from origin to consumption – are well understood in the manufacturing industry.

In fact the manufacturing companies have invested millions of dollars in software to optimize their supply chain management.

Within the professional services industry, the concept of a fully integrated and optimized SCM process is not commonly applied. But market trends and related challenges are driving the need for professional services provide to apply a similar supply chain concept in their organizations: talent supply chain management.

Challenges for SC management and future prospects

The research reported here reveals the substantial gaps between theory and practice. One central challenge is to the very idea of “managing” the supply chain.

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Who could and should have this responsibility? Arguably one ideal would be a separate function independent of the existing array of functions which are partially but not fully involved.

First, supply chain management can be seen as part of a wider set of trends involving outsourcing, cross-boundary working, new organisational forms characterised by flattened hierarchies, teams, and empowerment and so on rather than rigid command and control

Second, the trend towards outsourcing and the increasing importance of intangibles heightens the need for, and the potential of, supply chain management

Third, the trend towards fragmentation and variety in product and service offerings necessitates greater thought and skill in managing decoupling points and postponement of final product composition. Hence, the drivers impelling attention to crucial issues of alignment are certainly present but this does not mean that the task is given to supply chain specialists

Fourth, globalisation necessitates greater attention to logistics and to other component elements of supply chain management

Concluding Thoughts

There is every reason to be optimistic about the state of supply chain management research and practice, and the impact that supply chain management has had on the world. The favorable results achieved by companies, the growth of supply chain management as a major field of study across universities and its popularity among both students and employers supports that SCM works. The Wall Street Journal recently reported that more universities are adding SCM majors and increasing their programs as demand for SCM majors grows among employers.

To be effective, SCM must adapt to support an organization's competitive advantage. There is a common set of principles that underlie supply chain management—issues such as information transparency, supplier segmentation, customer service, lean principles, quality, improved communication, segmentation, inventory management, and more. In reality, they apply differently in different industries and companies, based on their competitive strategies. This does not mean that people in SCM do not have focus or direction. A true discipline has many aspects that are applied differently in different situations. For example, industrial

marketers apply their marketing mix very differently than consumer products firms to effectively serve their very different customer base.

That said, the change of mindset triggered by the constellation of forces as described in this paper and elsewhere could provide the opportunity for sophisticated and capable managers to engage in practices which approximate to the vision as described above. There could be a professionalisation opportunity here, or at least a pathway for further occupational development.

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